

Gender Differences On School Engagement Among Pre-Primary School Pupils In Oyo Township

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ABSTRACT

Academic engagement depends on a variety of factors and these factors can have both a positive and/or negative influence on a child's ability to stay motivated and succeed in school. Despite these challenges on academic engagement, some children are resilient and overcome the negative circumstances exposed to or thrust upon them. The study tends to fill the gaps on the factors that lead to low/poor academic engagement; It is in view of these concerns that this study was carried out to determine gender differences on school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. The study adopted a descriptive research design. A total of two hundred and fifty (250) pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township using simple random sampling technique. Questionnaires consisting of socio-demographic characteristics section, and standardized scales were used to collect data on academic engagement $\alpha = .84$. Two research questions were tested and answered using frequency distribution, percentage and Test at 0.05 level significant. The findings showed that the level of academic engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township is high ($x = .269 > 2.50$) and that there was significant difference in school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township ($T_{(248)} = .352, p < .05$). In conclusion, there was gender difference on school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. School administrators and government would understand the fact that providing good infrastructures such as building, library, computers and other school materials lead to academic engagement and excellent learning outcomes.

Keywords: Academic engagement, pre-primary school, gender, pupils

INTRODUCTION

School is central to the daily life of many pupils. They view schooling as essential to their long-term wellbeing, and this attitude is reflected in their participation in academic and non-academic pursuits. These pupils tend to have good relations with school staff and with other pupils – they feel that they belong at school. However, some pupils do not share this sense of belonging, and do not believe that academic success will have a strong bearing on their future. These feelings and attitudes may result in their becoming disaffected from school. They may gradually withdraw from school activities, and in some cases participate in disruptive behaviour and display negative attitudes towards teachers and other pupils.

Meeting the needs of pupils who have become disaffected from school is perhaps the biggest challenge facing teachers and school administrators.

However, Wang, Willett and Eccles, (2019) have recently used the term engagement to refer to the extent to which pupils identify with and value schooling outcomes, and participate in academic and non-academic school activities. Its definition usually comprises a psychological component pertaining to pupils' sense of belonging at school and acceptance of school values, and a behavioural component pertaining to participation in school activities. Albers (2017) defined engagement as active participation in the school and considered it a key concept to understand highschool failures, leading to negative individual social side effects and drop-outs. van Rooij, Jansen, , & van de Grift, (2017) considered absenteeism as the most important indicator of disengagement and unhappiness in school and as an important precursor of dropping out of school.

The psychological component emphasises pupils' sense of belonging or attachment to school, which has to do with feelings of being accepted and valued by their peers, and by others at their school. Another aspect of the psychological component concerns whether or not pupils value school success do they believe that education will benefit them personally and economically (McFarland, Cui, Rathbun, and Holmes, 2018). Pupils who do not feel they belong at school, or reject school values, are often referred to in the literature as alienated or disaffected. The participation component of engagement is characterised by factors such as school and class attendance, being prepared for class, completing homework, attending lessons, and being involved in extra-curricular sports or hobby clubs. Engagement is seen as a disposition towards learning, working with others and functioning in a social institution, which is expressed in pupils' feelings that they belong at school, and in their participation in school activities. It has yet to be examined whether disengagement from school during the adolescent years will have longer term effect.

Academic engagement is defined as the student's psychological commitment and effort to learn, understand, and acquire knowledge, skills, and technology that are directed toward academic work (Mercer, and Dörnyei, 2020). According to previous studies, academic engagement consists of three or four components. The three-component model, which this study used, has been widely accepted. The three components are behavioral engagement, affective engagement, and cognitive engagement. Pupils that are academically engaged in learning exhibit an effort to succeed in school (Li & Lerner, 2013). Hence, a significant number of high school learners are disengaged, not academically successful, and more likely to be depressed, unemployed, involved in criminal activities and delinquency.

Also, Appleton, Christenson, and Furlong (2008) considered pupils' engagement as person-centered approaches because it is a non-cognitive (meta-construct) factor that holds potential to get success in intended goals, especially at secondary school level. Fredricks (2015) stated that academic engagement is higher in classrooms where learners established interpersonal skills; where learners' autonomy is considered; where consistent and clear feedback is given to learners; where teachers hold high expectations; and where meaningful, interesting and challenging tasks are given to learners. In her later work, she also found that the biggest challenge in classrooms for teachers is learner disengagement (Fredricks, 2016). Disengagement leads to educational problems such as learner boredom, separation, high dropout rates, and low achievement (McFarland, Cui, Rathbun, & Holmes, 2018).

Researchers, educators, and policymakers are increasingly focused on academic engagement as the key to addressing problems of low achievement, student boredom and alienation, and high dropout rates (Peng, Li, Li, Jia, Wang, and Sun, 2019). Academic engagement measures have been shown to correlate positively with achievement and negatively with the likelihood of dropping out of school. Engaged pupils are more likely to earn better grades and perform well on standardized tests (Arias-Chávez, Vera-Buitrón, Ramos-Quispe and Pérez-Saavedra, 2020). The importance of academic engagement with school is recognized by educators, as is the observation that far too many pupils are bored, unmotivated, and uninvolved, that is, disengaged from the academic and social aspects of school life.

Another variable in this study is gender, therefore, to better understand why traditional notions of masculinity and femininity might impact school engagement in males and females, it may be helpful to define the constructs of sex and gender. Within a research context, sex can be defined as the objective

definitions of male, female or transgender, based upon defined biological characteristics. Gender on the other hand refers to socially constructed attitudes and beliefs about the attributes and behaviours associate with males and females (Hasan, and Khan, 2015). Characteristics are traditionally classified as masculine and feminine according to the degree to which they reflect gender norms.

According to a social constructionist viewpoint, gender norms can be enacted via gender scripts. Gender scripts are social schemas describing how boys and girls 'ought to' behave and what it means to be masculine and feminine in a traditional or even archetypal sense (Ajai, and Imoko, 2015) as this determine their level of school engagement. Over time, gender scripts become normative and can be seen as obligatory within a society. The ideals include scripts outlining how a boys or girls is supposed to act in order to demonstrate masculinity or femininity. Amogne, (2015) found that male scripts typically presume a boys be competitive, a provider and protector, and having mastery and control over their emotions and engage more in school activities. Traditional feminine gender scripts presume that a girls will strive to be attractive, bear and nurture children and engage in family life than school.

Especially in contemporary Western contexts, gender scripts can be enacted independently of biological sex, for example, boys can enact femininity or each sex might enact a combination of both scripts (Gull, 2018). However, enacting traditional gender scripts that are aligned to one's biological sex is still often encouraged, and failure to comply can result in the experience of gender role strain. Gender role strain is the cognitive conflict that results when an individual challenges or is unable to live up to traditional gender norms. Evidence relating masculinity to school engagement is complex however, and simple causal implications do not always apply. For example, a meta-analysis studies concluded that traditional masculine ideals can offer positive resources for boys engaging more in school than the girls. (Krumm et al, 2017). Therefore, this paper study examine gender differences on school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township.

Statement of Problem

Academic engagement depends on a variety of factors and these factors can have both a positive and/or negative influence on a child's ability to stay motivated and succeed in school. Reports have shown that there has been a downward trend in academic engagement of pupils in Nigerian secondary school in general. These investigations highlight the challenges posed by high rates of home and neighborhood violence and crime, increased levels of mental illness, poor-quality schools, and multiple family stressors that potentially interfere with children's adjustment and success in school as well as in other aspects of their lives. Parents, teachers, Curriculum experts have also expressed considerable concern about the level of academic engagement of the pupils. So also are teachers and school counsellor.

Despite these challenges on academic engagement, some children are resilient and overcome the negative circumstances exposed to or trusted upon them. One would then ask why do some children beat the odds while others experience poor outcomes such as school drop-out due to unable to adjust to school? These unhealthy behaviours of pupils which in turn impacts negative academic engagement make the researcher to ask "why are pupils not very concern about the current trend on their positive adjustment in school? All this questions serve as gaps for this study. The study tends to fill the gaps on the factors that lead to negative academic engagement; It is in view of these concerns that this study was carried out to determine gender differences on school engagement among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township.

Research Questions

Three research questions were asked and answered:

1. What is the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township?
2. Is there any significant differences on school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive survey design approach. The descriptive survey design allows the researcher to gather information, summarize and interpret data for purposes of clarification and

descriptive survey design is useful in collecting information about peoples' attitudes, opinions, habits or perceptions about issues under investigation.

Population

The study population for this study comprise of pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township. This consists of pupils in KG and nursery classes.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A total of two hundred and fifty (250) pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township was used for this study, the pupils were selected through simple random sampling technique. This technique was adopted because the target participants have homogeneous characteristics and they have equal chances of being selected for the study considering the four local government which are .Oyo west, Oyo East, Afijio and Atiba. The sample includes males and female pupils of primary schools, the researcher focused on pre-primary school pupils who are already spends years in school because they already have more experience in school on academic engagement. In total, 10 schools was considered in this study. The sum of twenty-five (25) respondents were used in each school in Oyo Township. In this paper, 101 (40.4%) of the respondents are males and 149 (59.6%) of the respondents are females. This means the females have higher population in this study than males in this study. Also, 217 (86.8%) of the respondents are Christian while 33 (13.2%) of the respondents are Muslim. Hence majority of the respondents are Christian.

Instrumentations

Questionnaire was used for data collection because of the study population. The questionnaires were divided into sections which are; A and B. section 'A' taps information on the socio-demographic characteristics of the participants like gender and religion. Section 'B' taps information on academic engagement which was filled by the teachers of the pupils

Academic Engagement Scale

Academic engagement scale was developed by Appleton, Christenson, & Furlong, (2008). This scale is used for measuring the pupils dive deep into learning activities, when they are mentally and emotionally absorbed by the study materials, and often when interacting with peers. The scale has a variety of items with different response scales and formats. The scale consists of 18 items and each item was rated using 5 point Likert scoring scale which include; Strongly Agree = 5 to Strongly Disagree = 1. Two sample items are: 1). "I do my homework (work about the school) on time" and 2). "I spend a lot of time on my studies and homework". The developers reports the reliabilities of 0.84.

Procedure of Data Administration

The researcher administered the questionnaires in the selected primary schools with the help of the teachers and research assistants. After permission was granted by the school authority, explanation was made to the teachers during the administration. There were made to understand the importance of participating in the study and essence of the research and the procedure of administration. The researcher assured them of confidentiality as the study did not look into their privacy and the results of the findings was only used for academic purposes.

Method of data analysis

The researcher made use of frequency distribution, percentages and T test to measure the differences of the study variable and was tested at 0.05 level of significant.

RESULTS

This section presents various findings drawn from the study on gender differences on school engagement among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township. The following results presented are based on the research questions raised generated which the study sought to answer.

Research Question

Research Question 1: *What is the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township?*

Table 1: Showing frequency distribution on the level of school engagement

Items	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{x}	SD
1. I spend a lot of time on my studies and homework.	80 32.0%	164 65.6%	5 2.0%	1 0.4%	3.29	.521
2. I give all my attention to the lesson in the class.	117 46.8%	77 30.8%	33 13.2%	23 9.2%	3.15	.974
3. I do my homework (work about the school) on time.	42 16.8%	103 41.2%	63 25.2%	42 16.8%	2.58	.959
4. I work as hard as I can at my lessons.	47 18.8%	89 35.6%	55 22.0%	59 23.6%	2.50	1.050
5. I do my best in class.	63 25.2%	70 28.0%	60 24.0%	57 22.8%	2.56	1.101
6. I don't give up trying even when the lessons are hard.	56 22.4%	73 29.2%	62 24.8%	59 23.6%	2.50	1.084
7. I believe I do my best to learn in class.	60 24.0%	64 25.6%	77 30.8%	49 19.6%	2.54	1.061
8. I try my best when working on my lessons.	53 21.2%	67 26.8%	77 30.8%	53 21.2%	2.52	1.050
9. I usually plan before doing my homework.	52 20.8%	92 36.8%	68 27.2%	38 15.2%	2.63	.978
10. I work on my lessons even when there are no upcoming exams.	58 23.2%	69 27.6%	72 28.8%	51 20.4%	2.54	1.061
11. I share the knowledge I learned at school with other people.	51 20.4%	78 31.2%	68 27.2%	53 21.2%	2.51	1.042
12. I check mistakes in my homework.	52 20.8%	71 28.4%	76 30.4%	51 20.4%	2.50	1.038
13. I often get into trouble in school.	45 18.0%	74 29.6%	76 30.4%	55 22.0%	2.44	1.025
14. I often get into fights in school.	40 16.0%	82 32.8%	67 26.8%	58 23.2%	2.42	1.021
15. I am usually sent to the disciplinary board because of my behavior.	71 28.4%	87 34.8%	55 22.0%	37 14.8%	2.77	1.023
16. I play truant from school every chance I get.	47 18.8%	109 43.6%	67 26.8%	27 10.8%	2.70	.896
17. I am usually late for school.	78 31.2%	139 55.6%	17 6.8%	16 6.4%	3.12	.791
18. I have considered dropping out of school.	86 34.4%	149 59.6%	8 3.2%	7 2.8%	3.26	.651
Weighted mean = 2.69						

Table 1 above shows the frequency distribution on the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. I spend a lot of time on my studies and homework. (\bar{x} =3.29) was ranked highest by the mean score rating on level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township and was followed in succession by I have considered dropping out of school. (\bar{x} =3.26), I give all my attention to the lesson in the class. (\bar{x} =3.15), I am usually late for school. (\bar{x} =3.12), I am usually sent to the disciplinary board because of my behavior. (\bar{x} =2.77), I play truant from school every chance I get. (\bar{x} =2.70), I usually plan before doing my homework. (\bar{x} =2.63), I do my homework (work about the school) on time. (\bar{x} =2.58), I do my best in class. (\bar{x} =2.56), I believe I do my best to learn in class. (\bar{x} =2.54), I work on my lessons even when there are no upcoming exams. (\bar{x} =2.54), I try my best when working on my lessons. (\bar{x} =2.52), I share the knowledge I learned at school with other people. (\bar{x} =2.51), I work as hard as I can at my lessons. (\bar{x} =2.50), I don't give up trying even when the lessons are hard. (\bar{x} =2.50), I check mistakes in my homework. (\bar{x} =2.50), I often get into trouble in school. (\bar{x} =2.44) and I often get into fights in school. (\bar{x} =2.42) respectively. The table shows the weighted mean of 2.69 which is greater than the standard mean of 2.50. This implies that the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township is high. That is, pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township involve is high level of school engagement and different activities such as games, class, quiz and others.

Research Question 2: *Is there any significant differences on school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township?*

Table 2: Summary Table of t-test for independent measures showing comparison of school engagement based on gender

	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	T	Sig
School engagement	Male	101	91.79	10.95	248	.352	.549
	Female	149	99.92	11.19			

From Table 2, the result showed that there was significant difference in school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township ($T_{(248)} = .352, p < .05$). From the table above, a mean score of 91.79 for male participants while female participants had a mean score of 99.92 with a mean difference of 8.13 and statistically significant. This implies that male (boys) and female (girls) level of school engagement differs.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the findings on the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township. The findings shows that the weighted mean was greater than the standard mean. This implies that the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township is high. That is, pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township involve is high level of school engagement and different activities such as games, class, quiz and others. Pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township engage themselves in school based on factors such as teachers, parents, peers, food and activities in schools. This has help to increase their learning outcomes; academic performance and attitude towards learning. This is inline with the study of Green et al. (2012) also found a similar pattern, showing that behavioral and school engagement explained the association between general academic ability and student achievement. Maltese et al. (2012) found a significant positive relationship between school engagement and achievement on standardized test scores. These findings indicated that students who completed any amount of homework earned higher test scores compared to their peers who did not complete homework. Holt (2007) suggested that there is a need to incorporate self-efficacy training into secondary education curricula, which in turn will empower educators to contribute to enhancing the school engagement of their

students. Indeed, the findings indicated that students who are strong in emotional management could control and apply emotional states by maintaining or changing their feelings and dealing well with frustration. Pope, Roper and Qualter (2012) found that a higher grade point average amongst post-secondary students, was “significantly related to higher scores on five individual EI competencies: conscientiousness, adaptability, empathy (sensing others’ feelings and perspectives), organisational awareness and building bonds (networking and building/maintaining relationships). In this study, empathy, organisational awareness and building bonds are competencies related to the social awareness cluster of competencies, whereas adaptability and conscientiousness are self-management competencies” Also, findings on significant differences on school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township shows that there was significant difference in school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. This implies that male (boys) and female (girls) level of school engagement differs. In this study, female engage more in school than the female. This is in support with the study of Marsh et al. (2016), showed that school engagement and achievement were mutually related, each fueling the other based on gender. They also found that student achievement and school engagement lead to later classroom effort, but that effort did not contribute to achievement and school engagement. Among elementary students, Viljaranta et al. (2014) have identified that performance leads to school engagement and, in turn, to interest for math, suggesting that school engagement is a process linking achievement to school engagement. Parker, Hogan, Eastabrook, Oke, and Wood (2006) found that “students who persisted had significantly higher levels of total EI than students who withdrew before the start of second year. Students who persisted had significantly higher levels of interpersonal, intrapersonal, adaptability, and stress management abilities than students who withdrew” as measured by the Emotion. Miller, Smith, Best and Hellsten-Bzovey (2013) found that students with higher scores in school engagement have a higher persistence, registration in the second year of their program. This research is significant as it has been conducted at a Canadian mid-sized university and early results are indicating EI level can be predictive of persistence.

CONCLUSION

This study is on gender differences on school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. In conclusion, this study revealed that that the level of school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township is high. That is, pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township involve is high level of school engagement and different activities such as games, class, quiz and others. Pre-primary school pupils in Oyo Township engage themselves in school based on factors such as teachers, parents, peers, food and activities in schools. Also, there was significant difference in school engagement based on gender (male and female) among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. This implies that male (boys) and female (girls) level of school engagement differs. Overall, the results of this study demonstrate that the academic engagement problems have become increasingly common among students nowadays, especially pre-primary school pupils who are prone to psychological problems. Researchers have shown that the poor academic engagement appears to be a very crucial and critical issue among pupils who are changing academic environments from a structured environment (course-taking) to a more unstructured environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study can serve as a baseline study for further investigation. It is recommended that further studies be conducted to further explore the gender differences on school engagement among pre-primary school pupils inn Oyo Township. The following are recommendation are suggested that; Pupils in general should be encourage in the community and religious bodies on how to developed and maintain good academic engagement as this will help them increase their academic performance. Also, early childhood educators and other educational professions should intervene in primary schools and help pupils who suffer or have low/poor academic engagement.

School administrators and government would understand the fact that providing good infrastructures such as building, library, computers and other school materials lead to academic engagement and excellent learning outcomes.

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